

Application of Interim Ecological Monitoring in protected area "Complex Ropotamo" based on Sentinel-2 data

Kamelia Radeva¹, Silvia Kirilova²

¹Space Research and Technology Institute – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria

²University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Hydraulics and Hydrology Department, Bulgaria
e-mail: Kamelia.Radeva@space.bas.bg; kirilova_fhe@uacg.bg

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Abstract: In the present study, interim ecological monitoring (IEM) is carried out in part of the territory of protected area "Complex Ropotamo", with the aim of tracking the dynamics of the ecosystem development. In the application of IEM, satellite data is used and with the help of NDVI and NDWI indices, the presence or absence of vegetation and water areas is established, as well as the dynamics of the development of vegetation and water levels in the studied territory are tracked. The obtained NDWI results are compared with the values of the total monthly precipitation and the monthly distribution of the annual runoff observed in a weather station (Ws) near the village of Veselije for two hydrological periods. Based on the obtained values of the NDWI index and their comparison with average total precipitation, a direct correlation between the average total precipitation and the spatial distribution of the average NDWI values for the studied period has been established. The direct relationship between the average total precipitation and the water areas formed in part of the adjoining lands of Ropotamo river explains the constant presence of water, which, on the other hand, creates favorable conditions for the development and maintenance of certain plant species in this section of the protected area. On the basis of the results, it can be concluded that remote sensing data can serve as a reliable source of information in monitoring the conservation status of habitats in and/or parts of or entire territories of protected areas.

Прилагане на междинен екологичен мониторинг в ЗЗ „Комплекс Ропотамо“ на базата на данни от Sentinel-2

Камелия Радева¹, Силвия Кирилова²

¹Институт за космически изследвания и технологии – Българска академия на науките

²Университет по архитектура, строителство и геодезия, София, България
e-mail: Kamelia.Radeva@space.bas.bg, spacedgclima@gmail.com

Ключови думи: Междинен екологичен мониторинг, директива за местообитания, дистанционни изследвания, NDVI, NDWI, Sentinel-2, сумарни месечни валежи, годишен отток

Резюме: В настоящото проучване се извършва междинен екологичен мониторинг (MEM) на територия, която е част от защитена зона (ЗЗ) „Комплекс Ропотамо“ с цел да се проследи динамиката на развитие на екосистемата. При прилагането на MEM се използват спътникови данни и с помощта на индекси NDVI и NDWI се установява наличие или липса на растителност и водни площи, както и се проследява динамиката на развитие на растителността и водните нива в изследваната територия. Получените резултати на NDWI се съпоставят със стойностите на сумарния месечен валеж измерен в метеорологична станция "Веселие" за два хидроложки периода. На базата на получените стойности на индекса NDWI и тяхното съпоставяне със сумарните валежи се установява пряка зависимост между осреднения сумарен валеж и площното разпределение на осреднените стойности на NDWI за два периода. Пряката зависимост между сумарния валеж и образуваните водни площи в прилежащата част на р. Ропотамо, обяснява постоянното наличие на малко количество вода в изследваната част, което от друга страна създава благоприятни условия за развитие и поддържане на определени растителни видове в защитената територия. На базата на извършеното изследване може да се заключи, че данните от дистанционните изследвания могат да послужат като достоверен източник на информация при наблюдение на природозащитния статус на местообитания в и/или на части от защитени територии.

Introduction

Remote sensing technologies can provide quantitative data on different types of natural territories, for example habitats (number, areas) and their 'quality' (structure, distribution of individual plant species groups, habitat type, resilience) through spatial resolution¹ and time frequencies². Remote sensing increases the availability of information on changes in habitat quality characteristics, and their impact on multiple aggregate components of biodiversity at different spatial scales. There is a growing need to apply remote sensing in ecology in order to create a common language, framework and research approaches, to obtain timely reliable information on the current and changed distribution of biodiversity, ruled by the management of the process for maintaining the conservation status of habitats and species. Kerr and Ostrovsky (2003)³ describe three main points of remote sensing for environmental purposes. First, unsupervised land cover classification is used to rapidly determine plant species and habitats. Second, for assessing ecosystem functioning over large areas, integrated ecosystem measurements are not appropriate. Recently, remote sensing has been used to obtain biophysical indicators such as Leaf Area Index (LAI) and Net Primary Productivity (NPP), (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index - NDVI)⁴. Third, change detection is essential for environmental monitoring and given the robust and reliable nature of the remote sensing imaging process, a reliable source of information is provided for this purpose.^{3,5} Extrapolation of temporal analysis can serve to predict environmental change for a future period. An example can be an assessment of the results of applying anthropogenic pressure on land use for protected species. Many researches have been made about anthropogenic impacts on land-cover change and the extent of remaining habitats⁶ but the magnitude and rate of change in biodiversity within habitats are typically poorly quantified⁷. Many studies illustrate how ecological problems ranging from biodiversity loss to land-use change have benefited greatly from advances in geospatial technologies such as GIS and remote sensing, both in the provision of data and access to spatial data analysis tools. Interim ecological monitoring (IEM) could provide comparative data and information on which base the factors responsible for observed changes in different types of natural areas like protected areas, habitats, forests, wetlands and other different types of water bodies can be identified whenever possible from satellite data. Radeva (2018) reviews the aspects and perspectives of interim ecological monitoring as part of ecological monitoring by means of aerospace data with different spectral and space resolution and in relevance of object type to be monitored. Interim ecological monitoring based on remote sensing helps identification of biodiversity elements that are underrepresented in conservation areas and thus it is useful for modelling disturbed landscapes.⁸ The shape and spatial distribution of landscape elements reveal characteristics of the processes in these landscapes and are therefore important to consider^{9,10}. Spatial patterns of land cover are often highly sensitive to changes in landscape function and character and therefore a good indicator of dynamics^{11,12}. A key point when using remote sensing is the selection of appropriate satellite data and methods for further processing and verification with ground data. Different indicators of ecosystems that best characterize their condition can be used to evaluate the results of applying IEM using aerospace data. Various indices, classifications and correlations between different states of ecosystems can be used as such indicators.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

We selected a territory with an area of 756.30 ha (tested area) that is part of PA "Complex Ropotamo" (BG0002041), which is located in South-Eastern Bulgaria in the boundaries of the municipalities of Primorsko and Sozopol. The territory falls within the scope of the Black Sea Basin Directorate for Water Management - Southern Coast. In 2009 Ministry of the Environment and Water announced the complex is a protected area upon Habitats Directive 2009/147/EC, with a total area of 3857.75ha, which also includes the Ropotamo Reserve with an area of 1000.7ha.¹³ The studied area has a conservation importance since habitats 92D0, 91 EO and 91 ZO are situated in its territory or nearby, but all within the boundaries of PA "Complex Ropotamo".

Fig. 1. Location of the investigated area - PA "Complex Ropotamo" (BG0002041)

Fig. 2. Location of the territory in the adjoining lands of river Ropotamo within PA "Complex Ropotamo" (BG0002041)

In terms of climate, the territory of PA "Complex Ropotamo" falls into the Continental-Mediterranean climate region with the Burgas lowland and the Strandzha coast, the relief helps for the formation of precipitation in the studied area. The Mediterranean influence additionally contributes to

the formation of precipitation maxima in November and March, and the minimum is determined in July - August. The climate in the area is defined by mild winter, early spring, hot summer and warm autumn. Favorable conditions for the vegetative development of the vegetation in the area with a period of about 7m with stable retention of air temperatures above 10°C.

Approach

The Methodology for Interim ecological monitoring (MIEM) includes the investigation of certain parameters and indices for the condition of a certain ecosystem in different time intervals. The methodology enables the formulation of realistic assessment for the ecological condition of the ecosystems as it analyzes the change of dynamics in ecosystems based on different indicators for assessment and effect on the processes and interactions. The "parameters" on which different indicators for ecosystem condition assessment are considered to be the essential element in the methodology. The following group parameters should be considered 1) productivity, including both floral and faunal components; 2) biodiversity, defined by the variety of floral and faunal species existing in the natural area, in terms of community composition and structure, as well as the functional niches that are represented; and 3) resistance to changes in structure and function and persistence over long periods of time, that depends on the area, water balance, climate components, natural hazards, external influence from impacts of industrial or anthropogenic natures. The quantitative assessment under the methodology has been accomplished based on the following formula¹⁴

$$(1) \quad \Delta A_{t_j, t_m}^i = A_{t_j}^i (P_1^i, P_2^i, \dots, P_k^i) - A_{t_m}^i (P_1^i, P_2^i, \dots, P_k^i)$$

$$(2) \quad \Delta A_{t_j, t_m}^i = \begin{cases} < 0 \\ = 0 \\ > 0 \end{cases}, \text{ where } j \in 1, n; m \in j, 1 \leq m \leq n,$$

where:

$\Delta A_{t_j, t_m}^i$ – Assessment for temporal intervals before and after the application of interim ecological monitoring for a certain ecosystem type (i)

$A_{t_j}^i$ – Assessment for temporal interval before the application of interim ecological monitoring for a certain ecosystem type (i)

$A_{t_m}^i$ – Assessment for temporal interval at the time of interim ecological monitoring application for a certain ecosystem type (i)

$P_1^i, P_2^i, \dots, P_k^i$ - indexes group group parameters 1),2),3) presented herein

For the purpose of the present research interim ecological monitoring in PA BG0002041 "Complex Ropotamo" has been applied analyzing indices from parameter groups 1) and 3). Based on formula (1) we investigated the spatial distribution of the vegetation (NDVI), water surface (NDWI) and climate component (precipitation) for a 5 –year period (2019-2023).

$$(3) \quad \Delta A_{march_{2019}, october_{2023}}^{PA\ BG0002041} = A_{march_{2019}}^{PA} (P_1^{PA}, P_3^{PA}) - A_{october_{2023}}^{PA} (P_1^{PA}, P_3^{PA})$$

where:

PA BG0002041 – is the identification number for protected area "Complex Ropotamo"

P_1^{PA} - parameters from group 1 for the protected area "Complex Ropotamo" (NDVI, NDWI)

P_3^{PA} – parameters from group 3 for the protected area "Complex Ropotamo" (precipitation)

Data sources and processing

For the purposes of the present study satellite images from Sentinel 2 A, C for the spring-summer and autumn-winter seasons from 2019 up to 2023 and meteorological data for total precipitation measured in weather station (Ws) "Veselie" and data from other researches have been used. The selection of suitable satellite images for visualizing the water areas and vegetation cover in the studied area was carried out according to the availability and accessibility of satellite data from Sentinel 2 A, C satellite. Remote-sensing data is delivered by Copernicus Hub:

<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home> and from <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/explore/eobrowser/>,

presented in Table 1 below. Part of the total precipitation data presented in Table 2 is provided by NIMH. The information array of data on the monthly amount of precipitation in Ws “Veselie” for the purposes of the study is divided into two periods from 1981-2023 and from 2019-2023. Table 2 presents the annual distribution of total precipitation per months for both periods.

Table1. Remotely-sensed derived data

Year	Date	Satellite	Year	Date	Satellite
2019	24.03	Sentinel 2 L2A	2021	22.5.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	23.4.	Sentinel 2 L2A		19.9.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	23.5.	Sentinel 2 L1C		19.10.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	30.9.	Sentinel 2 L1C	2022	28.3.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	10.10.	Sentinel 2 L1C		27.4.	Sentinel 2 L1C
2020	13.3.	Sentinel 2 L1C		12.5.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	17.4.	Sentinel 2 L1C		9.9.	Sentinel 2 L2A
	12.5.	Sentinel 2 L1C	24.10.	Sentinel 2 L1C	
	24.9.	Sentinel 2 L1C	2023	8.3.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	19.10.	Sentinel 2 L2A		2.5.	Sentinel 2 L1C
2021	3.3.	Sentinel 2 L1C		24.9.	Sentinel 2 L1C
	12.4.	Sentinel 2 L1C		24.10.	Sentinel 2 L1C

Table 2. Annual distribution of total precipitation per month P[mm] ,Hs “Veselie”

Periods/Months	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
2019-2023	85.2	63	46	73.8	23	68.8	23.4	19.8	53	47.8	95.25	91.75
1981-2023	74.8	65.2	56.3	53.3	47.1	44.1	36.2	26.6	52.4	65.0	80.9	67.5

Primary and secondary processing of satellite data from Sentinel 2 was performed. The primary processing consists of channel selection to create composite images of the NDWI and NDVI indices. Secondary processing consists of generating area data from the created composite NDWI and NDVI images with the ArcMAP tools.

Results

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is one of the indices that can be analyzed in order to generate data for the status and spatial distribution of the vegetation ¹⁵. For the purpose of the study, the NDVI enables the evaluation of the overall change in vegetation regardless of the plant species composition. We have defined the NDVI values using the following value classification: *No vegetation (0.1)*, *Open soil (0.1-0.2)*, *Sparse vegetation (0.2-0.4)*, *Moderate vegetation (0.4-0.6)*, *Dense vegetation (0.6-1)*. (Fig. 3, images a-x, Fig. 5). The results for “*Dense vegetation*” indicator show an interesting trend: a significant increase in the area occupied by dense vegetation in the autumn period, from 268.95 ha (in September 2019) to 488.96 ha (in September 2020) and 560.64 ha (in September 2022) and stable values between 540.53 ha, which is the lowest value recorded in May, 2023 and 575.7 ha, which is the highest value recorded in May, 2021. For the “*Moderate vegetation*” indicator (0.4-0.6), a drastic change in the areal distribution of vegetation in 2019-2020 is observed, with a sharp increase in the occupied area of *moderate vegetation* from 202.85 ha in 2019 to 429.78 ha in 2020, a sharp decrease in the spatial distribution in 2020-2021 with an area from 429.78 ha to 56.93 ha respectively. The reasons for the changes can be derived by additionally analyses using other vegetation indices like disturbed index (DI), Normalized Difference Greenness Index (NDGI), etc.

Analyzing Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) is of great importance for the study, since it contributes to estimate the water area and is suitable for appropriate definition of “water- land”¹⁶. The results show that in most of the studied territory the NDWI values are below zero, which confirms absence or presence of very little water in the territory (Fig. 4, images a-x, Fig. 6). Interesting case is the territory situated in the adjoining lands of river Ropotamo, in southern-eastern part of the studied territory (Fig. 2). The NDWI rates are between 0-0,2 (“*flooding, humidity*”), with a rapid increase

registered in March 2019-2021 and in October 2019 and 2023. At the same time during March –April in the period 2019-2023 the spatial distribution of NDWI is within the ranges 0.2-0.3 (*water surface*) and 0.3-1.0 (*water surface*) (see Fig. 4, images b,f,k,l,p,j,o,u,v) which indicates for water areas availability. Taking into consideration this trend and that the location of the territory is in the adjoining lands of River Ropotamo, it was necessary to analyze the precipitation values. The correlation between the average NDWI values for a 5-year period and the total precipitation for the same period could not be established. The reason is that the available data for total precipitation derived from Ws “Veselie” refer to a very short period, from 2019-2023 (Fig. 7, Table 2). From a statistical and hydrological point of view, the larger the range of values of a given meteorological quantity, the smaller the fluctuations of the random quantity around their mean value. Thus, the higher NDWI values that we detected from remotely-sensed data can be explained only with a direct correlation. Consequently, the comparison was made between the NDWI values with the precipitation values for a longer period from 1981 till 2023 (Fig. 8, Table 2).

The results demonstrate a direct correlation between average total precipitation [mm] (top on fig.8) and average values of water areas¹⁷ [ha] (bottom on Fig. 8) presented by months. The precipitation-runoff trend is observed and confirmed, namely, with the increase in precipitation (March/October), the water surface in the studied area in the PA “Complex Ropotamo” also increases.

Conclusions

The application of interim ecological monitoring (IEM) enables to generate information for the status of the researched area and detection of change in certain ecosystems. Analyzing remotely-sensed indices like NDVI and NDWI from Sentinel-2 contributes to assess the ecological conditions for maintaining the conservative status within the tested area. Since the methodology for IEM gives possibility for investigation of different parameters, we could establish the importance of the direct correlation between the average total precipitation and the run-off of Ropotamo river. Moreover, the application of IEM based on remote sensing tools helped to establish the necessity of further monitoring on habitats condition situated in the adjoining lands of River Ropotamo and further researches on climate change influence in the PA “Complex Ropotamo”.

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of NDVI in test area within PA “Complex Ropotamo” for the period 2019-2023

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of NDWI in test area within PA "Complex Ropotamo" for the period 2019-2023

Fig. 5. Distribution of NDVI values by dates to the researched area for the period 2019-2023

Fig. 6. Distribution of NDWI values by dates to the researched area for the period 2019-2023

Fig. 7. Annual distribution of total precipitation Ws “Veselie” per months for the period 2019 - 2023 to average total water surface per months within researched area in PA”Complex Ropotamo” upon NDWI ≥ 0.2

Fig. 8. Annual distribution of total precipitation Ws "Veselie" per months for the period 1981 - 2023 to average total water surface per months within researched area in PA "Complex Ropotamo" upon NDWI ≥ 0.2

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